

FRACTURE MECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF PULL-OUT AND FRAGMENTATION TESTS

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SUMMARY: The aim of this paper is a clarification of the failure process taking place in pull-out and fragmentation tests as well as a critical assessment of the common techniques for the evaluation of the experimental data. The fracture process is analysed by means of the finite element method. In the pull-out test, the mode ratio changes dramatically during the first phase of the crack from dominating mode I to mode II. The mixed mode energy release rate is calculated for glass fibers embedded in a thermoplastic matrix. It turns out that the strain energy stored during the cooling process, significantly increases the energy release rate in the pull-out test and has to be taken into account in the evaluation of the test data. In the fragmentation test, a mode II failure arises. Due to the existence of high radial compressive stresses in the interface, frictional shear stresses develop, which result in a strong decrease of the energy release rate and must not be neglected in the evaluation of the test data.

KEYWORDS: pull-out test, fragmentation test, energy release rate, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

For a long time, the micromechanical tests were used for the determination of the strength of the interface between fiber and matrix. However, for the determination of the strength, the stress state must be well defined. In the micromechanical tests, a complex, threedimensional stress state is encountered around the interface [1-3]. Severe stress concentrations arise at the fiber break in the fragmentation test and at the fiber end as well as at the fiber entry in the pull-out test. Within the linear theory of elasticity, singularities are found at these points, similar to a crack tip. Under those circumstances, it is not reasonable to conduct a stress analysis in order to calculate an interfacial strength, because the stresses at the critical points depend on the local geometry and on the local material properties, which may differ significantly from that of the bulk material. Moreover, not only one isolated stress component is found at these points but a superposition of radial and shear stresses. The ratio of the two components strongly depends on the material properties of fiber and matrix. In the past, substantial simplifications concerning the stress field around the interface were used for the evaluation of the test data. One model, based on a plastic behaviour of the matrix [4], presumes an unbounded yielding of the matrix near the interface, leading to constant interfacial shear stresses (Kelly-Tyson formula). The two main inconsistencies inherent in this approach are the neglect of the other stress components and the unrealistic strains resulting from the unbounded yielding of the matrix. The other model simplifies the elastic stress field using the shear lag hypothesis [5,6]. This model is inconsistent in that it results in constant axial stresses in the matrix, violating the boundary conditions in the interface and, furthermore, underestimates the stress concentrations at the critical points [7]. A further

problem of the measurement of the strength with pull-out tests is the definition of the moment of failure initiation. Several studies have shown that the failure initiation arises long before the force maximum is reached [8,9].

In recent years, the characterisation of the interface by a fracture mechanical analysis leading to a fracture toughness or an energy release rate, becomes more and more accepted [1,10-15]. A fracture mechanical analysis is more adequate to the stress state arising in the interface with stress singularities at the critical points. However, not all problems encountered in the stress analysis are overcome. As a result of the superposition of radial and shear stresses, only a mixed mode fracture toughness can be measured directly. The discrimination of the modes requires a theoretical analysis [16]. In general, the fracture toughness can be determined experimentally, if the material behaves perfect linear elastically and if the variation of the compliance with the crack length can be measured with high precision. However, the determination of the crack length is not possible for all matrices and it is a rather complicated procedure [9]. Furthermore, polymeric matrices exhibit a more or less nonlinear behaviour. The linear elastic analysis, which is commonly utilised in the literature, gives a first approach and offers some insight into the main mechanisms of the fracture process, if the matrices are not too nonlinear.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The pull-out test model consists of a fiber of ten microns in diameter embedded perpendicular into a halfsphere of matrix up to a length of 150 microns. The fragmentation test model of 400 microns in length corresponds to one half of a fragment, applying symmetry conditions at the edges. For both specimens, axisymmetrical finite element meshes are used (figs. 1a, 1b). The meshes are strongly refined around the interface with respect to the high stress gradients arising

Fig. 1: Finite Element meshes (a: pull-out test, b: fragmentation test)

there. In the interface, contact elements are defined together with links between the two anticipated crack faces, which can be removed in order to simulate the crack propagation. The aim of the present analysis is to study of the variation of the interfacial stresses and of the energy release rate during interfacial failure. To this end, the propagation of an interface crack is simulated, however, not controlled by a failure criterion but prescribed externally.

FAILURE PROCESS IN PULL-OUT AND FRAGMENTATION TESTS

The process of interfacial failure is totally different in the pull-out and in the fragmentation test. If the initial stresses due to the thermal mismatch of fiber and matrix or due to curing are not taken into account, the interfacial stresses in the pull-out test build up continuously with the increase of the external force up to the initiation of the interface crack. In the fragmentation test, on the other hand, the loading of the interface starts abruptly with the breakage of the fiber. This is, the interface is loaded rather statically in the pull-out test while dynamically in the fragmentation test. A further essential difference between the respective tests is the correlation between the prescribed external load and the loading of the interface. While the load at failure initiation is correlated to the strength of the interface in the pull-out test, it is correlated to the fiber strength in the fragmentation test. This means that the onset of interfacial failure cannot be controlled by the external force in the fragmentation test. Therefore, the crack propagates unstably after the breakage of the fiber. Furthermore, the type of crack is different. In the pull-out test, a pure interface crack arises while in the fragmentation test it is often observed that the interface crack is preceded by short matrix cracks, both, in 90° and 45° direction [14].

STRESS FIELD AROUND THE INTERFACE

The stress field around the interface arising in the pull-out and fragmentation test is analysed for a glass fiber embedded in a polycarbonate matrix with a stiffness ratio of 32. The specimen is cooled down by 120°C, frictional stresses are not included at this stage. In the pull-out specimen, the thermal mismatch leads to an inhomogeneous stress field around the interface. The fiber is under axial compressive stresses reaching a maximum in the middle part (fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Thermal stresses in fiber in interface in the pull-out test

The fiber stresses are accompanied by interfacial shear stresses which change their direction along the fiber. Two maxima occur, one at the fiber entry and a second one at the fiber end. In addition, compressive radial stresses arise in the interface except of the fiber entry, where a high tensile stress maximum is encountered. If the pull-out force is applied, the compressive

stress state is changed to tensile one, starting from the fiber entry (fig. 2, fig.3). However, during the first phase of the crack, still compressive stresses arise near the fiber end. With the further propagation of the crack, this zone decreases until the fiber is completely under tensile stresses.

Fig. 3: Axial fiber stresses in pull-out specimen at different crack lengths $a[\mu\text{m}]$

By the application of the pull-out load, the shear stresses at the fiber entry are increased while they are decreased at the fiber end (fig. 2, fig. 4). With the initiation of the interface crack, the maximum at the fiber entry is further increased remaining almost constant during further crack propagation, while the average of the shear stresses grows due to the reduction of the stress transfer length. The radial tensile stress maximum at the fiber entry is also enhanced by the application of the external force (fig. 5). However, it drops by an order of magnitude by the initiation of the crack, again, remaining almost constant during further crack propagation. This is, while the radial tensile stresses are dominating before the onset of failure and are, accordingly, responsible for the crack initiation, the shear stresses are dominating during the further crack propagation. This is, the ratio of the failure modes changes with crack initiation.

Fig. 4: Interfacial shear stresses in pull-out specimen at different crack lengths $a[\mu\text{m}]$

Fig. 5: Interfacial radial stresses in pull-out specimen at different crack lengths $a[\mu\text{m}]$

In the fragmentation specimen, the effect of the thermal mismatch on the stresses around the fiber is rather small. If the specimen is loaded, the fiber is under constant axial tensile stresses except of the ends of the specimen. After fiber breakage, the fiber stresses decrease very rapidly in the vicinity of the fiber break or, after crack initiation, at the crack tip, respectively (fig. 6). The maximum fiber stresses remain nearly unchanged by the crack extension.

Fig. 6: Axial fiber stresses in the fragmentation specimen at different crack lengths $a[\mu\text{m}]$

Additionally, very high shear and radial compressive stresses arise in the interface near the break point (fig.7, fig.8). Both stress components are significantly decreased due to the initiation of the interface crack. Contrary to the pull-out specimen, the interfacial failure is governed by shear stresses in the fragmentation test since the radial stresses are compressive. These give rise to frictional shear stresses in the debonded zone, consuming a lot of released strain energy.

Fig. 7: Interfacial shear stresses in fragmentation specimen at different crack lengths $a[\mu\text{m}]$

Fig. 8: Interfacial radial stresses in fragmentation specimen at different crack lengths $a[\mu\text{m}]$

ENERGY RELEASE RATE

In case of a perfect linear elastic material behaviour, the critical energy release rate does not depend on the crack length. If the course of the energy released during crack propagation, for example under fixed loads or fixed grips conditions, is known, the fracture process can be characterised, i. e. stable or unstable phases can be discriminated. To this end, the energy release rate arising in the pull-out and fragmentation test is calculated. In the pull-out test, fixed load conditions are prescribed, corresponding to the level at failure initiation as observed in the experiments. In the fragmentation test, fixed grips conditions are prescribed, corresponding to the strain to failure of the fiber. However, the unloading of the total specimen due to the propagation of the interface crack is very low, likewise resulting in an almost constant load. The force in the middle of the fiber decreases by only 0.7 % due to the fiber break and by 0.5% by a crack of two fiber diameters. This means, on the other hand, that the compliance of the fragmentation test specimen is rather insensitive against the crack length.

Pull-out Test

The energy release rate arising in a pull-out test increases very slowly over a large range of the crack in case of a frictionless interface, if thermal stresses not taken into account [17]. In case of a thermoplastic matrix, a large portion of energy is stored in the specimen as a result of the cooling process. The fiber is compressed while the matrix around the fiber is under tensile stresses. If the interface crack propagates, this energy is released. Furthermore, the external work done by the pull-out force acting at the fiber tip is increased by the additional displacement of the fiber tip as a result of the initial stresses. The energy release rate without thermal stresses increases slowly, until the crack approaches the fiber end, where the increase becomes very steep (fig. 9). Due to the thermal stresses, the energy release rate is enhanced significantly. This is, the initial stresses have to be taken into account, if pull-out experiments are evaluated. However, this part of stored energy is often neglected in the literature.

Fig. 9: Energy release rate arising in pull-out test with and without thermal stresses

Fragmentation Test

The course of the energy release rate of a fragmentation test is totally different from that of a pull-out test. With the breakage of the fiber, a large amount of stored energy is released, which is much higher than that dissipated by the fiber break. The unused energy causes an unstable interface or matrix crack. In general, both cracks may develop simultaneously. The process occurring directly after fiber break is very complex and requires an analysis including dynamical effects. However, no reliable local material data are given at present for the respective matrices under high speed conditions. The present analysis, therefore, is confined to static conditions, which are valid for the second phase of stable crack propagation.

First, the released strain energy as a result of the fiber fracture and the interface crack is inspected. The total amount of released energy as well as the contributions of fiber and matrix are shown in figure 10. By the fracture of the fiber, the fiber is unloaded, releasing a large amount of strain energy. This value is represented by the starting point. At the same time, the matrix is stressed additionally, consuming energy. This process continues during the extension of the interface crack. The accumulated released energy increases due to crack propagation, however, with decreasing slope. Beyond a crack length of about one fiber radius,

the released energy grows rather linearly, resulting in an almost constant energy release rate, as shown below.

Fig. 10: Energy released by fiber and matrix in fragmentation test

The energy release rate of an interface crack is plotted in fig. 11 with and without interfacial friction. The first point represents the energy released by the fiber break per cross-section of the fiber. In the first phase of the interface crack, the energy release rate is extremely high. It drops, however, to about 20% of the maximum value within a crack length of only 20% of the fiber diameter. Beyond this region, the energy release rate slightly decreases, leading to a stable crack propagation. In order to get an estimation of the upper limit of the influence of friction, the same system is analysed allowing frictional stresses with a friction coefficient of 1.0. As a result of friction, the energy release rate decreases significantly to about one quarter of the original value. This shows that the evaluation of test data requires the knowledge of the work of friction.

Fig. 11: Energy release rate arising in fragmentation test with and without friction

CONCLUSIONS

In general, the interfacial fracture toughness can be determined using pull-out and fragmentation tests. However, while in pull-out tests the compliance is sensitive against the crack length, this is not true in case of the fragmentation test. This means, the fracture toughness can be measured with an acceptable accuracy directly in the pull-out test, if the matrix is transparent and behaves rather brittle. In the fragmentation test, on the other hand, an additional theoretical analysis is needed. For such an analysis, the external force necessary to cause a stable crack propagation must be measured. This may be complicated due to the fact that multiple fiber fractures and, accordingly, multiple interface cracks usually are present in a fragmentation test. A further problem arising in the fracture mechanical evaluation is the existence of radial cracks.

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crack was propagated fifty millimetres before the test specimen was unloaded. The foam-based systems E and F were not evaluated in this part of the study.